

Preliminary Chemical Examination of the Bark of *Holarrhena Antidysenterica*.

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In a detailed communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 559) on the isolation and characterisation of three new bases from the Indian *Holarrhena* we have already described the method employed for the extraction of the alkaloid, which gives more than twice the yield of total alkaloid, so far obtained by any of the previous authors and conessine in a yield about four times as high as any, referred to in literature. Payman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 163), however, had got 0.25% conessine from *Holarrhena Congolensis* Stapf, and Giemsa and Halberkann (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1918, 256, 201) 0.7% conessine and 1.7% total alkaloid from *Holarrhena Africana*. As the different authors have used very varying methods for the extraction of the alkaloids, it appeared to us of great interest to compare the yield of alkaloids obtained by these different methods from the same sample of bark to test and establish the value of the method evolved by us. Also we found it desirable to make a cursory examination of the non-alkaloidal constituents.

As a result of these investigations we have found out that the ammonia-alcohol-ether mixture employed by us is the best means of extracting the alkaloids, which occur in the plant body as tannates, which are very difficultly soluble in alcohol or acidulated alcohol or water, but are easily liberated from their tannic acid salts by alkalis. The physiological action of the crude bark and its extract in the treatment of intestinal troubles, may also be due to this fact as the tannates of the alkaloids would remain undissolved in the acid juices of the stomach and pass on to the seat of disease in the intestines.

Besides isolating a tannate of the alkaloids we have detected the presence of linoleic acid as a component of the fatty matter and isolated in quite a large yield liquid sterols and a crystalline sterol which we have identified to be lupeol.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Different methods of extraction of the alkaloids were tried with the same sample of powdered bark and the results obtained are given in the following table. In each case the alkaloid was finally purified by dissolving out with ether containing 10% alcohol. The number of percolations and the quantity of solvent used in each case was the same.

Extraction media.	Mode of separating the alkaloids.	Yield.	Remarks.
1. Cold alcoholic percolation.	Alcohol removed under reduced pressure and alkaloids extracted from residue.	1.05%	Method used by Ghosh & Ghosh (<i>J. Indian Chem. Soc.</i> , 1928, 5, 477), yield 1.28% in assay and 0.7% in large extraction.
2. Same.	Solvent distilled off under ordinary pressure.	0.5	There was some resinous basic residue insoluble in ether-alcohol.
3. Soxhleted for 16 hrs. with alcohol.	Solvent distilled off under ordinary pressure.	1.4	Basic resinous residue, insoluble in alcohol and ether,
4. Percolated with ether containing 10% of alcohol and 2% liq. ammonia.	Alkaloids extracted with dilute acetic acid.	1.7	
5. Alcohol containing 10% liq. ammonia.	Made faintly acidic with acetic acid; alcohol distilled under reduced pressure.	1.75	
6. Treated with 10% alc. KOH then percolated with ether containing 10% alcohol.	Made faintly acidic with acetic acid, solvent distilled off, finally under reduced pressure.	1.53	
7. Percolation with very dilute HCl	Made faintly alkaline with $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$. Extracted the dried precipitate with petrol and the filtrate with ether.	0.8 yielded crude conessine (m.p. 122°) 0.3%	Voluminous brown ppt. Giemsa & Halberkann (<i>loc. cit.</i>) got 1.7% by this method from H. African raw.

The best method of extraction was found to be method (4) followed by a further series of extractions using 80 parts ether and 15 parts alcohol mixed with 10 parts of liquor ammonia. By this method a total yield of 2.1% was obtained.

Insoluble tannate of the alkaloids.—500 G. of the drug, percolated with alcohol, yielded 22 g. of extractive on removal of the solvent under reduced pressure. To this 100 c.c. of water were added and the neutral products extracted off with ether. To the aqueous filtrate drops of sodium hydroxide solution were carefully added until the solution was just alkaline, when a rose coloured precipitate of the tannate was formed (7.5 g.) which was filtered off and dried. It was found to be insoluble in water or cold dilute mineral acids, partially soluble in alcohol and soluble in dilute acetic acid. The alkalis, as well as the boiling dilute mineral acids decompose it. Its solution in alcohol is coloured green by ferric chloride. A trace of alkali changes it to violet. On decomposition with caustic soda it yielded about 20% by weight of alkaloids, traces of a resinous acid

and an acid filtrate which gave the usual colour reactions of a tannin of the phlobaphene group.

The Neutral Products.

Lupeol.—The ether soluble neutral products left after the extraction of the alkaloids from the ether-alcohol-ammonia percolates of the drug (yield 2% on weight of dry bark) were saponified in the usual manner, yielding 1.2% of unsaponified matter and 0.5% of fatty acids. The unsaponifiable matter yielded 0.2% of crude lupeol directly out of alcohol and further 0.4% of it through acetylation of the mother liquors. After repeated recrystallisation from alcohol and ethyl acetate, pure lupeol was obtained in star shaped aggregates of needles, m.p. 213-14°. In a 2.06% chloroform solution it showed a rotation of $D^{35} = +27.4^\circ$. The melting point given for lupeol is 210° and the rotation noted for it by previous authors is variously given from +25.95° to +27.4°. (Found: C, 84.3; H, 11.8. $C_{31}H_{50}O$ requires C, 84.9; H, 11.8 per cent). Lupeol acetate prepared in the usual manner, melted at 214°. (Found: C, 82.1; H, 11.0. $C_{33}H_{52}O_2$ requires C, 82.5; H, 10.8 per cent). Lupeol benzoate melts at 266°.

Uncrystallisable sterol.—The unsaponifiable matter further yielded a brownish glassy solid which melted to a viscous liquid between 25-30° (0.3%). It could not be distilled at a pressure of 5 mm. (showing thereby that high aliphatic alcohols are absent), but gave all the usual colour reactions of sterols with Burchard Lieberman's, Salrowski's and Moleschott's tests and appeared to be an uncrystallisable sterol.

Fatty acids.—(Yield 0.5% on wt. of the bark). These were separated by the lead method into solid acids (0.13%), m. p. 58-70° and liquid acids (0.35%). The latter on bromination in a mixture of glacial acetic acid and ether yielded a small quantity of an insoluble bromide, m.p. 174-76°, which appeared to be linolenic acid hexabromide. About half of the remaining bromides, when recovered, were found to be soluble in petrol and the other half insoluble. The liquid acids, therefore, appeared to be a nearly equal mixture of oleic and linoleic acids with a trace of linolenic acid and were not further investigated.

